

Room-Temperature Film Formation of Metal Halide Perovskites on n-type Metal Oxides: The Catalysis of ZnO on Perovskite Crystallization

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We investigate the effect of commonly used solution-processed TiO_x, SnO₂ and ZnO interlayers on the perovskite film crystallization process. We find that the ZnO/perovskite interface can efficiently catalyze the perovskite crystallization even without thermal annealing.

Metal halide perovskites have emerged as promising materials for a range of optoelectronic applications, including solar cells, light-emitting diodes (LEDs).^[1-3] In a typical perovskite solar cell or LED device, n-type metal oxide films, such as solution-processed TiO_x,^[4] SnO₂^[5] and ZnO^[6], are widely used as the electron-transport layers (ETLs) to facilitate the perovskite crystallization and enable efficient electron extraction/injection at the interface. Solution-processed ZnO with suitable energy levels and optoelectronic properties, hence has been successfully employed in optoelectronic devices processed from organic and quantum dot semiconductors.^[7-8] However, the perovskite optoelectronic devices processed on ZnO, especially the perovskite solar cells, always exhibit inferior device performance and poor stability compare with that on TiO₂ and SnO₂.^[9] Recently, it has been demonstrated that with proper surface modification via functional interlayers, the interfacial reaction between perovskite films and ZnO can be efficiently surpassed, leading to obviously improved device efficiency of perovskite solar cells and LEDs.^[10-12] Unfortunately, the operational stability of ZnO-based perovskite optoelectronic devices is still moderate. Considering the recent advances of the use of ZnO in perovskite optoelectronic devices, a deep understanding of the interaction between perovskite and ZnO is expected to give more insights to further improve the device stability.

perovskite crystal structure during the thermal annealing.^[9] In addition, the residual functional groups at the surface of solution-processed ZnO, e.g. hydroxyl groups and acetate ligands, accelerate the interfacial reaction under elevated temperatures, resulting in a fast thermal decomposition of perovskites to PbI₂.^[9] Unlike the well-investigated perovskite decomposition process on ZnO, the effect of ZnO/perovskite interface on the perovskite crystallization process is rarely reported. The main reason is due to the simultaneous decomposition and crystallization processes of perovskites happened on ZnO under thermal annealing, making it hard to distinguish the two processes.

Herein with the introduction of a room-temperature vacuum-processing method, we decouple the film decomposition and crystallization processes of perovskite on the n-type metal oxide substrates. We systemically investigate the film formation of methylammonium lead iodide (MAPbI₃) perovskite on the commonly used metal oxide ETLs, i.e. TiO_x, SnO₂, and ZnO. Through optical and structural characterizations of the resulting perovskite films, we find that the reaction at the ZnO/perovskite interface happens at the beginning of the perovskite crystallization process. With the removal of the organic components during vacuum-processing, only the films

Fig. 1 a) UV-Vis absorption spectra and b) normalized PL spectra of perovskite films that deposited on different substrates before (dash lines) and after (solid line) vacuum-processing. The inset is the PL spectra of perovskite films before after vacuum-processing.

processed on ZnO exhibit good perovskite crystallinity while the crystallization of MAPbI₃ on TiO_x and SnO₂ is obviously retarded. The good photoluminescence (PL) of the films and decent device performance indicate excellent optoelectronic properties of the resulting perovskite films on ZnO. Our observations reveal that the reaction at the ZnO/perovskite interface does exist even without any impetus from thermal annealing, helping to catalyze the perovskite crystallization

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In previous studies, detailed theoretical calculations have been performed to explain the chemical instability of ZnO/perovskite interface, and many hypotheses have been proposed to reveal the possible decomposition paths. It is well-accepted that the basic nature of ZnO may facilitate the proton-transfer reactions at the ZnO/perovskite interface, resulting in destroy of the

process. In addition, we also demonstrate that with the modification of ZnO using an interfacial polymeric surface modifier of polyethylenimine ethoxylated (PEIE), the ZnO/PEIE interface exhibits similar surface property as TiO_x and SnO_2 . This leads to efficient suppression on the interfacial reaction happened between ZnO and perovskite.

To prepare the metal oxide substrates, SnO_2 , TiO_x precursor solution and the ZnO nanoparticles dispersion are prepared and deposited on pre-cleaned ITO substrates according to previous literature.^[1, 5, 13] The perovskite films are deposited on different n-type metal oxides via solvent quenching method in glovebox, with the dimethylformamide (DMF) as the precursor solvent and toluene as the anti-solvent.^[4] For the vacuum-processed films, the as-spun films are placed in a vacuum chamber (-1 Bar) under dark and kept at room temperature for 12 h (see details in experimental section of the supporting information).

We carry out a range of film characterizations to investigate the perovskite formation process on different metal oxides. We show the ultraviolet-visible (UV-vis) absorption spectra of the perovskite films deposited on TiO_x , SnO_2 and ZnO substrates before and after vacuum-processing in Fig. 1a. We notice that there is negligible change of the film absorption on TiO_x and SnO_2 before and after the vacuum-processing and no absorption from crystallized perovskite is detected. Surprisingly, although the absorption of the as-spun perovskite film on ZnO is similar with that on TiO_x and SnO_2 , a clear

attributed to the intermediate phase and crystallized MAPbI_3 perovskite, respectively. After the vacuum-processing, the PL emission at ~ 718 nm disappears and the PL emission from perovskite become dominant, implying efficient formation of well crystallized MAPbI_3 perovskites on ZnO substrates. The red shift of the PL spectra may be attributed to promoted crystallization and enlarged grain sizes of perovskites on ZnO during the vacuum processing. The PL intensity of the perovskite film processed on ZnO is also much higher than that on TiO_x and SnO_2 , suggesting better crystallinity of perovskites processed on ZnO (see inset PL spectra in Fig. 1b). We conclude from the optical characterization results that crystalline perovskite films form only on ZnO under the room-temperature vacuum-processing, while the perovskite crystallization process is significantly inhibited on TiO_x and SnO_2 metal oxide substrates.

To further investigate the crystal structure changes of perovskites on different metal oxide substrates, we perform the X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements and show the results in Fig. 2. From the XRD patterns of thin films on TiO_x and SnO_2 , we only observe slight enhancement of the intensity but little changes of the typical peaks before and after the vacuum processing. The crystal property is almost the same on these two metal oxides, consistent with the characterization results of the absorption and PL spectra. We attribute the weak peaks at 14.1° and 28.3° to (110) and (220) planes of the tetragonal phase MAPbI_3 perovskite, respectively. We also detect the

Fig. 2 X-ray diffraction pattern of perovskite films deposited on ZnO, SnO_2 and TiO_x substrates: a) before vacuum-processing; b) after vacuum-processing. The XRD patterns are all normalized by the (220) peaks that are located at 28.3° .

absorption from crystallized perovskites is observed after vacuum processing. The optical bandgap of the film calculated using a Tauc plot of the absorption spectra is ~ 1.60 eV, which matches well with that of MAPbI_3 perovskite. In Fig. 1b, we show the photoluminescence (PL) spectra of thin films deposited on different metal oxides before and after the vacuum processing. We observe only one typical PL emission peak located at around 680 nm from the as-spun films on TiO_x and SnO_2 . The PL peaks show slight red shift to 702 nm after vacuum processing. By contrast, for the as-spun film on ZnO, we clearly observe two emission peaks from the PL spectrum, one located at ~ 718 nm and another at ~ 780 nm, which can be

typical peak corresponds to PbI_2 at 12.8° together with possible intermediate phases of PbI_2 -MAI-DMF at 13.1° from films on TiO_x and SnO_2 .^[14-15] However, the as-deposited film on ZnO exhibits much higher XRD intensity from crystalline perovskite and produces a preferential orientation of (110) plane after the vacuum-processing. Since we use the anti-solvent to promote the fast perovskite crystallization during the film deposition, we assume that the as-spun films consist of a large amount of small perovskite crystals along with the intermediate phases.^[16] The different XRD results of the as-spun films on different metal oxides reveal that the perovskite crystallization depends strongly upon the surface properties of the bottom substrates.

The effect of ZnO on the perovskite crystallization starts from the initial perovskite crystallization stage, leading to more obvious crystalline perovskite formation. We observe further crystallization and coarsening of perovskite proceed during the vacuum-processing with the remove of excess organic components (Fig s1). However, without enough driving force from the thermal annealing, the perovskite crystallization on TiO_x and SnO₂ is retarded, while the interfacial reaction at ZnO/perovskite interface catalyse the perovskite crystallization.

The promoted film crystallization and enlarged grain sizes of perovskite on ZnO are further confirmed by scanning electron microscope (SEM) characterizations shown in Fig. 3. We compare the top-view SEM images of the films on different substrates before and after vacuum-processing. We observe slightly enhanced crystallinity from the as-spun films on ZnO compared with that on TiO_x and SnO₂. For the vacuum processed films, we clearly find that the crystallization of perovskite is much obvious on ZnO substrates with grains larger than 300 nm. In comparison, the perovskite crystallization is significantly suppressed on TiO_x and SnO₂ substrates, consistent with our XRD results.

Fig. 3 SEM images of perovskite films that deposited on ZnO, SnO₂ and TiO_x substrates before (a-c) and after (d-f) vacuum-processing, respectively. The scale bar is 1 μm.

To investigate the optoelectronic properties of the obtained perovskite films, we fabricate perovskite LEDs based on the vacuum-processed perovskite films on these three metal oxides. The ZnO, SnO₂ and TiO_x films in the LEDs function as electron injection layers while the commonly used poly(9,9-dioctyl-fluorene-co-N-(4-butylphenyl)diphenylamine) (TFB) is deposited on top of perovskite films as the hole injection layer (device geometry is shown in Fig. 4a). We note that although the top view of the perovskite on ZnO shows many voids, the cross-sectional SEM images of the perovskite (shown in Fig. s2) demonstrates a continuous layer. The external quantum efficiency-voltage (EQE-V) curves and the current density-voltage-radiance (J-V-R) curves are depicted in Fig 4b and 4c. The maximum EQE, maximum radiance, EL peak, turn on voltage (V_{th}) of devices based on different substrates are all summarized in Table 1. The devices based on SnO₂, TiO_x exhibit poor performance with the EQEs less than 1%, while the ZnO-based perovskite LEDs show much improved device performance, with the maximum EQE of 3.03 % at 2.8 V and a

high radiance of 58.8 W/(sr*m²). The normalized EL spectra of the LEDs on different substrates is depicted in Fig. 3d (all obtained at 2.5 V). The EL peak of device based on ZnO is located at 762.4 nm, which is consistent with the emission from MAPbI₃ perovskite. We observe that the EL emission peaks for devices on SnO₂ and TiO_x are significantly blue-shifted to around 725 nm. The decent device performance further confirms the good optoelectronic properties of the vacuum-processed perovskite films on ZnO.

In previous reports, solution-processed ZnO was proven

Fig. 4 a) The device geometry of perovskite LED; Device performance of perovskite LEDs with different substrates: b) EQE versus current density curves; c) current density and radiance - driving voltage curves; d) Normalized EL spectra of the devices on ZnO, SnO₂ and TiO_x substrates.

capable of accelerating the decomposition process of perovskite films under thermal annealing.^[9] We believe that the deprotonation of the organic cations at the perovskite/ZnO interface under mild condition is helpful to initiate and promote the perovskite crystallization. In addition, since ZnO is synthesized from acetate salts and the surface ligands cannot be completely removed.^[8] We also need to note the function of residual acetate ligands of ZnO on the perovskite crystallization. It has been well demonstrated that the introduction of a trace amount of acetate-based additives could decrease the activation energy (E_a) of perovskite crystallization.^[17-18] In addition, the incorporation of lead acetate into perovskite precursor solution can also promote the formation of dense and continuous films.^[16, 19-20] We anticipate that the surface acetate ligands of ZnO have the similar effect as acetate ion in the

Table 1 Devices performance of perovskite LEDs that based on different substrates

precursor on reducing the E_a promoting the perovskite crystallization.

Devices	EQE (%)	Radiance (W/(sr*m ²))	EL peak (nm)	V_{th} (V)
ZnO	3.03	58.8	762.4	1.6

SnO ₂	0.58	0.6	728.8	1.8
TiO _x	0.37	0.3	725.8	1.5

We notice that the PEIE is commonly used to modify the surface of ZnO for efficient perovskite optoelectronic devices, especially the perovskite LEDs. To verify the effect of PEIE modification on ZnO substrates, we perform the same vacuum-processing of perovskite film on ZnO/PEIE substrates. We follow the optimized recipe for efficient perovskite LEDs and introduce a thin layer of PEIE (0.04 wt%) on top of the ZnO film. We carry out detailed optical and structural characterizations on the films before and after vacuum-processing and show the results in the supporting information (Fig. S3-S5). We find that with the insertion of a thin PEIE layer, the perovskite crystallization process on ZnO/PEIE behaves similarly with that on TiO_x and SnO₂. The obtained perovskite films exhibit the same retarded optical, structural properties and film morphology.

In conclusion, we investigated the perovskite film formation process on the commonly used n-type metal oxides under room-temperature vacuum-processing. We observed much different crystallization process of perovskites on ZnO compare with that on TiO_x and SnO₂. We anticipate that the chemical interaction at the ZnO/perovskite interface, either from the basic nature of ZnO or the residual acetate ligands, can decrease the activation energy for the perovskite crystallization. With the introduction of a thin PEIE surface modifier, the interaction between ZnO and perovskites can be efficiently suppressed, leading to retarded perovskite crystallization and crystal growth. Our results reveal the effect of interaction at ZnO/perovskite interface on the perovskite crystallization and provide new insights to further development of ZnO-based perovskite optoelectronic devices.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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